

Methodology of Using Digital Technologies in Literature Lessons of Class 5-6

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Article information:

Manuscript received: 30 Oct 2024; **Accepted:** 03 Nov 2024; **Published:** 27 Dec 2024

Abstract: This in the article digital in the century education from transformation passing, information technologies (IT) of our lives indispensable to the part what has become and his all sciences, including literature sciences to learn about strengthen possibilities increased, general education literature in 5-6 grades of schools from IT technologies in his classes use methodology illuminated.

Keywords: 5-6 grade, information technologies (IT), digital tools, effective integration, program, purpose, use, lesson, education efficiency.

21st century education digital from transformation is passing . Information technologies (IT) of our lives indispensable to the part became and his all sciences, including literature sciences to learn about strengthen opportunities denial reached it won't be. This research general education literature in 5-6 grades of schools from IT technologies in his classes use methodology learns.

These methodology students for literary works in learning interesting, interactive and enriching experiences create from IT power for to use directed. It's just that technology to class from input out comes out; he is young in students to understand deepening, critical thinking development and creativity increase for own of possibilities to use strives.

This is 5-6 grade literature to classes information technologies efficient integration to do the basics defines:

1. Goals identify:

Information from technologies use according to study goals sure set put, deeper understanding, activity, critical thinking and the language to develop attention focus.

2. Correct tools select:

Online platforms (Google Classroom, Edpuzzle, Quizizz), digital tools (text processors, presentation programs) and digital libraries such as relevant IT tools choose.

3. Continuous integration:

IT tools traditional teaching methods to fill provide, active to learn encourage and from the students use according to sure instructions to give

4. Interesting events:

Virtual tours, interactive stories, multimedia projects, digital discussions, interactive games and students by created websites such as different different events done increase.

5. Evaluation:

Online activity through student's development watching to go, constructive feedback present reach and students needs and opinions based on the approach constant respectively evaluation and match.

General education in school digital from technologies use to us name gives:

- Digital literacy: In student's information from technologies efficient use for necessary digital to skills have to be provide.
- Usage possibility: all students, that's it including the disabled also use for opportunity has been the need solution to do
- Time management: information from technologies to use traditional methods with balancing, meaningful discussions and reasoning conduct for enough the time provide.
- Teachers qualification increase: numeric skills and confidence increase for professional development opportunities search.

Teachers this methodology used students of 5-6th grade to literature innovative methods with attraction do, read and to learn for life love wake up enable gives.

Information technology (IT) 5-6th grade literature to classes integration of student's activity, understanding and to learn significant level to increase can. Below is from IT efficient use methodology:

1. The goal identify:

- Text understanding: IT tools to the student's characters, plot, themes and literary devices analysis in doing help gives.
- Text with engage: Interactive actions and multimedia reading more interesting and impressive to do can.
- Critical thinking Development: Students different point of view views, research context learning and own interpretations formations can.
- Language skills reinforcement: information technologies word wealth increase, grammar practice and creative to write makes it easier.

2. Correct tools select:

➤ Online platforms:

- ✓ *Google Classroom*: resources share , tasks set ;
- ✓ *Edpuzzle* : To understand check for installed questions with interactive videos create ;
- ✓ *Quizziz*: to learn evaluation for interesting quizzes and games for;
- ✓ *Nearpod*: Multimedia and request features have interactive lessons for.

➤ Digital tools:

- ✓ Word processors: creative writing, editing and formatting for.
- ✓ Presentation program (PowerPoint, Google Slides): Literature in topics students by created presentations for.

- ✓ Audio and video editing program: Text related audio/video projects writing get and editing for.
- **Digital libraries and data bases :**
- ✓ Project Gutenberg: a classic of literature wide from the library free of charge use.
- ✓ Internet archive: books, films and another public information of means digital archive.
- ✓ The Britannica School: A Study goals for to age suitable encyclopedia.

3. IT no problem integrate:

- From technology addition as use: information technologies traditional teaching methods to fill need them not exchange need;
- Active to study attention Focus: Students from IT research, creativity, cooperation and critical thinking for to use encourage;
- Clearly instructions give: Readers selected from tools how efficient to use to understand trust harvest to do;
- Various events offer reach: students are interested and different different learning styles suitable will come.

4. Interesting events:

- Virtual tours: virtual tours through settings and historical the context study
- Interactive stories: in collaboration story to do for Storybird or like Comic Life from tools use.
- Multimedia projects create: Readers the text based on podcasts, videos or digital presentations to create encourage.
- Digital debates and discussions: literary topics discussion to do and analysis to do for online forums or discussion from the boards use.
- Interactive games and simulations: Basic concepts strengthening or historical events again create for online from the games use.
- Pupils by created websites: To readers known one book, character or literary period according to websites design.

5. Evaluation:

- Development watching Go: Online events and evaluations through of student's activity and understand watching to go
- Constructive feedback present Achievement: Personalized feedback and improvement according to suggestions present reach for from technology use.
- Reflection conduct and customization: IT integration efficiency constant respectively evaluation and students needs as well opinions based on your approach change.
- Information technologies education in the process apply through digital of means mountainous selection to us the following education efficiency gives:
- Digital literacy: Readers information from technologies efficient use for necessary digital literacy skills with equipped trust harvest to do
- Usage possibility: all students, including those with disabilities also use for opportunity account get.
- Time management: From technology excess of use prevention get and meaningful discussion and reasoning conduct for enough the time provide for your lessons

planning.

- Teachers qualification increase: Teacher's digital skills and confidence increase professional development for opportunities search,

Digital education in the environment right selected digital tools through IT tools for teachers thought out and strategic way own into received without, 5-6 grade students for interesting, enriching and remember remains literature lessons to create can.

5th-6th grade students for literature of IT technologies to classes integration education change for huge to potential have. Clearly defined methodology used without, teachers interesting, interactive and enriching experiences create for digital tools from strength their uses can.

This is the approach convenience for from technology simply from use out comes out; he is young in students to understand deepening, critical thinking development and creativity to turn on directed. Appropriate tools thoroughness with choice, various events own into get and students development observation through teacher's IT education improve for strong catalyst to be provide can.

This of methodology effect from class also available outside. XXI century digital literacy skills have has been students to technology more and more more dependent has been in the world movement to do for better are prepared . In them to literature relatively deeper respect appear will be, study and to learn for life love wakes up.

However, success constant professional development, developing to technologies adaptation and done increase efficiency constant respectively evaluation obligation depend This the approach used without, teachers young of student's literature to the world has been attitude and him appreciate methods change for of IT huge potential to open can.

Used literature:

1. Bekchonova Sh.B. Digital and information technologies. methodological manual. Publishing house "Lesson press", T.: 2022, 48 p.
2. "Pedagogical web design" textbook. "Tafakkur bostoni,, publishing house., Nukus-2023-y. 286 p.
3. Sh.B. Bekchonova, ZRSaidova, AZMakhmudov. Use of information technologies in professional activity. Tutorial. T.: New Century University. "Lesson Press" publishing house, 2023. 189 p.
4. Miguel Abreu , Luis Paulo Reis, Nuno Lau . Considering imperfect symmetry: A new extension of the actor-critic learning symmetry. arXiv :2309.02711 v 1 [cs . LG] September 6, 2023. <https://github.com/m-abr/Adaptive-Symmetry-Learning>. 1- 28 p.
5. M. Sall' e , J. Smit and J.C. Vink . Institute for Theoretical Physics, Valckenierstraat 65, 1018 XE Amsterdam, The Netherlands. New initial conditions for post-quench quantum field simulations. <https://arxiv.org/abs/hep-lat/0110093> v 1 . 1-3 pp.